

Implementation of English Language Learning Using Grammar Translation Method (GTM) To Improve Learning Outcomes of Grade 2 Students at SDS Al-Ittihadiyah

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ABSTRAK

English subjects focus on developing communication, comprehension, pronunciation, and writing proficiency. Teachers should use effective methods such as Grammar Translation Method (GTM) for grammar rules and translation. Educators must understand different teaching approaches to teach English effectively, such as GTM for vocabulary learning. Therefore, this research focuses on an in-depth study of how the Application of English Learning Using Grammar Translation Method (Gtm) to Improve Learning Outcomes of Grade 2 Students at SDS Al-Ittihadiyah. In this study using a qualitative approach with descriptive methods. Data collection techniques in qualitative research are observation, interviews, and documentation studies. In addition to using qualitative research, this research also uses literature research or library research. Based on the research and discussion, English teaching at SDS Al-Ittihadiyah has developed to keep up with globalization. The GTM method is used in grade 2, where students must be able to read and write English first. GTM focuses on grammar and vocabulary, with teachers using grammar analysis and translation. The main priorities of this method are reading, writing and translation skills. In addition, GTM has increased students' interest in translating Indonesian to English and helped teachers in evaluating students' learning outcomes. Overall, GTM is effective in improving students' ability to learn English.

PENDAHULUAN

Language is the most important means of communication that people can rely on in their daily lives and relationships. At the age of 4-7 years, it can improve the communication skills of children who have reached the optimal stage (Sondakh and Sya, 2022). Thus, teaching children aged 4-7 years a second language makes it easier for children to follow subsequent learning (Febriyanti, Hadi, & Saputri, 2018). English is a foreign language that is one of the compulsory local content lessons, as described in the Ministry of Primary and Secondary Curriculum Regulation No. 12 of 2024 (Ristek, and Indonesia, 2022).

English is a language that is used as a distinctive language, but is currently used as an international language to maintain communication between countries that use different languages. In general, the quality and efficiency of English education in Indonesia still needs to be improved, because on the one hand our average English proficiency is still lacking.

English has now become an international language, used in almost every aspect of global life and is associated with the transmission of information throughout the world. Learning English is considered important and cannot be ignored for children aged 7 to 12 years old who are usually in grades 1-5 of elementary school. This is because at this age children adopt an intellectual/cognitive development approach which at this age has reached the concrete activity stage created by Jean Piaget (1896-1980). At this stage children already have the ability to think logically, but only with concrete objects.

English subjects are required to develop the following four skills; a) communicating both orally and in writing, b) comprehension, c) ability to produce oral texts, and d) proficiency in written texts. Of the four language skills, writing is one of the productive skills. In this capacity, students' products become the final object of the whole English learning process (Mainandir, 2022).

Teachers should choose appropriate teaching methods when teaching English to students. Many methods can be applied and developed by teachers in the teaching and learning process in the classroom (Haryanto). In Indonesia, most schools do not use Grammar Translation Method (GTM) in teaching English, but other methods and techniques, one of which is the use of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT). As the

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grammar translation method emphasizes instructional accuracy, CLT emphasizes language fluency (Hesti, Dalman, & Carla, 2019).

To be successful in teaching English, you should know that there are several methods, one of which is the Grammar Translation Method (GTM), which is a method that teaches grammar rules whose main function is focused on translation and memorization of word forms (Hengki, Ratna and Rasyid, 2019). The GTM teaching method is a grammar and translation method that aims to encourage students to learn English vocabulary through memorization and translation. In addition, it is a word-for-word translation method suitable for all students' language levels (Ambarwati, Wiryasaputra, & Puspasari, 2017).

RESEARCH METHOD

The research method used in this research is a qualitative approach with descriptive methods. According to Sugiyono (2007: 1), qualitative research method is a research used to research on natural objects where the researcher is the key instrument, data collection techniques are combined, data analysis is inductive, and qualitative research results emphasize meaning rather than generalization.

Data collection techniques in qualitative research are observation, interviews, and documentation studies.

1) Observation

Observations made in this study are observations. This observation was made to Al- Ittihadiyah Elementary School students by giving assignments to students and answering questions directly.

2) Interview

Conducted to the teacher to see the extent to which grade 2 students can quickly understand the English material that has been taught.

3) Documentation Study

Documentation study in this research is needed to strengthen the research analysis related to learning English vocabulary about time (day) through memorization and translation.

Besides using qualitative research, this research also uses literature research or library research. Library research is collecting library data obtained from various sources of library information related to the object of research such as through abstracts of research results, indexes, reviews, journals and reference books (Sugiyono, 2010).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

English Language Learning

Learning is a unity of elements consisting of human elements, materials, facilities, equipment and methods that interact with each other to achieve learning goals.

Uno (2007:54) says that learning can be interpreted as a process of interaction between learners and teachers/ instructors and/or learning resources in a learning environment to achieve certain learning objectives. This shows that learning is an interaction between students and their environment so that changes occur for the improvement of behavior. The main principle in the learning process is a process that covers all or most of the potential of students and their meaning for themselves and their lives now and in the future. Thus, learning does not only occur between teachers and students, but also with other sources such as media and materials.

Language is a communication tool used by humans to convey messages from sender to receiver. Language learning does not grow by itself, but requires interaction with others. Children who grow up isolated from their social environment do not develop their own language. Humans have the ability to produce different sounds. These sounds are developed into meaningful symbols.

English is an oral and written medium. Whereas communication is the understanding and expression of information, thoughts, feelings and the development of science, technology and culture. In Indonesia, English is usually taught as a foreign language. The term "foreign language" in linguistics is different from the term "second language". A foreign language is a language that is not used as a medium of communication in the country where it is taught. A second language is a language that is not the primary language but is one of the most widely spoken languages in a country. Meanwhile, foreign languages are usually taught in schools as subjects that emphasize the basics of communication and mastery of the four language skills that all students must learn, including: (listening, speaking, writing, reading) in a foreign language. that language within certain limits. limits.

1. Listening is a skill that has been neglected due to the lack of materials for this skill in the form of textbooks and other tools such as audio recordings, which are exchanged for listening tasks from the teacher use in English.
2. Speech The main purpose of speech is to convey a message to others, which is the ability to communicate linguistically. The first goal can be achieved through action, while the second goal can be achieved through developmental practice.
3. Writing Writing is considered the most difficult skill compared to other language skills. When learners use a second language orally, native speakers may understand and accept less than perfect pronunciation. However,

when students use another language to write, native speakers will be more harsh in judging letters that contain many spelling or grammatical errors.

4. Reading Reading is a very difficult or difficult activity because it depends on the student's language skills and learning. A person's goal in reading is to understand or comprehend the content of the message contained in their reading as effectively as possible.

Reading involves the ability to recognize text and make inferences about the meaning of words using foreign vocabulary. Thus, children have the opportunity to learn any language, including learning English as a foreign language.

Meanwhile, Hapsari (2012) states that English language teaching in Indonesia for elementary school students is based on the Decree of the Minister of Education and Culture No. 060/U/1993 dated February 25, concerning the possibility of English language programs as a local content subject for elementary schools, and can be started in grade 4 (depdiknas). This policy was taken because of the need to participate in the era of globalization. In its development, English, which was originally an optional local content subject, became a compulsory local content subject in some regions. Furthermore, English lessons that initially began in grade 4 began in grades 1, 2 and 3.

In English learning that has been carried out at SDS Al-Ittihadiyah especially in grade 2, students begin to understand the material that has been taught quickly through the GTM method where students must first be able to read and write English.

Grammar translation method (GTM)

Grammar Translation Method (GTM) is one of the methods that need to be applied in teaching grammar to English language learners. This method is able to make a positive contribution in increasing their interest and ability as well as minimizing the obstacles in translating sentences from Indonesian into English.

Grammar and translation method is a teacher-centered method, where the teacher uses grammar and translation method to focus students' attention on grammar and vocabulary. The main basis of this method is the memorization of rules, grammatical analysis of discourse, and then translation into the language used as an introduction to the lesson. Very little attention is paid to speaking skills. This means that the emphasis of this method is not on training students to be good at communicating actively, but on understanding language logically based on careful analysis of aspects of grammatical rules."

To evaluate learning outcomes, students can apply GTM using question and answer techniques to students about the material that has been learned to measure and evaluate the extent to which students can digest and understand the lessons that have been learned (ahmad mizan).

In addition, teachers can also apply it by giving questions routinely given according to ability. The words that can be given are very diverse, starting from everyday verbs, nouns, and can also introduce themselves at a basic level (Murti, 2018).

GTM has its own characteristics and advantages in students' reading proficiency as opposed to the ability to memorize first. Among the characteristics of this method, namely; (1) prioritizing the ability of reading, writing, and translation skills; (2) utilizing students' native language as the language of instruction in the teaching and learning process; (3) positioning grammar as a means of learning foreign languages; and (4) the teacher focuses on analyzing grammar or grammar in sentences that are often studied (Rahman, 2012).

As for the results of the activities we have carried out in the application of the GTM method that has been given to grade 2 students of SDS Al-Ittihadiyah, the teacher provides an understanding of the material first then they are taught to be able to write, read and pronounce it one by one to the front of the class so that they can quickly memorize what material has been taught such as English vocabulary material about the day.

Picture 1. Material Provision

Then SDS Al-Ittihadiyah students are increasingly interested in translating Indonesian sentences into

English. Teaching styles, strategies and media that have been used by teachers can increase students' enthusiasm in learning. And can be directed according to the interests and talents possessed by students by motivating and systematic direction to students through these strategies (Sya, Anoegrajekti, Dewanti, & Isnawan, 2022).

Student Learning Outcomes

Wina Sanjaya (2010: 13) says that learning outcomes are related to achievement in acquiring abilities in accordance with the specific objectives planned. Thus the main task of the teacher in this activity is to design instruments that can collect data about the success of students in achieving learning objectives.

Through the use of this teaching method, it can enhance the quality of the teaching and learning process which in turn can affect the level of student learning outcomes. Therefore, the use of teaching methods is highly dependent on the learning objectives, teaching materials, the ease of obtaining the necessary media and the teacher's ability to use them.

The improvement of student learning outcomes in class 2 began to achieve the desired expectations through GTM because the learning model used can train children's memory when they are asked to come forward to mention the names of days directly, without looking at notebooks or writing on the blackboard.

Picture 2. Students come forward to say the names of the days.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research conducted and the overall discussion, it can be concluded that English language teaching in elementary schools has evolved to adapt to globalization, with some regions making it a compulsory subject since grade 1. In English language learning that has been carried out at Al-Ittihadiyah Elementary School especially in grade 2, students begin to understand the material that has been taught quickly through the GTM method where students must first be able to read and write English. The Grammar and Translation Method (GTM) is teacher-centered, focusing on grammar and vocabulary. The teacher uses grammar analysis and translation, with little attention to speaking skills. This method is characterized by:

1. Prioritizing reading, writing and translation skills.
2. Using the students' native language in teaching.
3. Positioning grammar as a means to learn a foreign language.
4. Analyzing grammar in sentences.

At SDS Al-Ittihadiyah, GTM has improved students' ability to read and memorize, such as learning the names of days in English. The teacher presents the material, then students write, read and pronounce it. This approach has increased students' interest in translating Indonesian sentences into English.

GTM helps teachers design data collection instruments to assess student learning outcomes. This teaching method can improve the quality of the teaching and learning process, which leads to improved student learning outcomes. The effectiveness of GTM at SDS Al-Ittihadiyah has been proven in improving students' memory skills.

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